

Consequences of Speed of Light as an Upper Bound on Space-time

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In Newtonian mechanics, there is no upper bound on velocity. It seems that if one keeps applying a force, then kinetic energy, momentum and speed should increase. If one wishes to retain the Newtonian idea of work increasing kinetic energy and momentum, but impose the notion of an upper limit to speed, then problems arise given that $KE = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$ and $p = mv$. In Newtonian mechanics, one also has the notion of a Galilean transformation, and it seems that by changing such a transformation to a Lorentz one, one may see considerations of an upper bound speed arise. This means, however, that for the upper bound speed, the notion of speed no longer comes from the moving frame, but strictly from dx/dt which must be physically controlled in some other manner, hence rendering the Galilean transformation obsolete for this upper bound speed b .

We first note (as in (1)), that one may consider a particle with rest mass, m_0 , at rest at $x=0$, $t=0$ and create a matrix which describes it as seen in a frame moving with constant $-v$. One finds that such a description involves a constant b (with units of speed) which is the same in all frames. We note that if there is an upper bound on speed, then no frame can increase this speed (unlike the Galilean case). Thus, the presence of a b is compatible with an upper bound to speed. Traditionally, special relativity starts with the notion of physical equations being the same in a frame moving with a constant speed relative to another. This suggests a rest frame. We suggest that one may derive the Lorentz transformation strictly by considering an upper bound to speed, i.e. $x/t=b$ in one frame and $x'/t'=b$ in another. This transformation also applies to a particle with rest mass, m_0 . In fact, it is the co-ordinate frames (x,t) and (x',t') which are rest-frame objects even for an upper bound b (as we show).

If one applies the same transformation to (p,E) , then one finds $E^2 = p^2b^2 + m_0^2c^4$. For $m_0=0$, one has: $E=pb$, where b is presumably the upper bound of speed. This equation shows that, consistent with Newtonian thinking, one may increase E and p , but now b does not increase. In (1), we suggested that $b=c$, i.e. the speed of light in a vacuum, and argued that there is no rest frame co-ordinate axes in a photon and so constant/ E and constant/ p have to represent time and space gradations for such a particle. Here, we argue that given that speed cannot increase as one increases E and p for a particle with no rest mass, so that E and p must control the gradations of t and x which ultimately define speed. In other words, E and p , which may be measured independently through heat generation and impact on a target, must also have physical effects on motion through space-time by changing dx and dt (for $m_0=0$). Furthermore, this upper bound on speed also exists for a particle with rest mass. Even though m_0 breaks the $E=pc$ relation, the notion of E and p still affecting spacetime gradations does not need to disappear. In fact, we argue that a particle with rest mass must carry a physical signature of the upper speed bound at any speed. We have noted in previous notes that $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m_0^2c^4$ for small m_0c^2 essentially leads to $E \approx pc$ and so in such a case the time-space gradations should approximately hold. The presence of c in the special relativistic equations were noted in (1) to be a sign of this upper bound signature, but no immediate physical attribute can be assigned to c in such equations it seems. We suggest that

the photon feature: constant/E and constant/p is this required physical feature which ultimately regulates that speed cannot increase even as E and p do.

Newtonian Mechanics

Newtonian mechanics suggests that one may apply a force to an object which has rest mass and increase its $KE = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$, momentum $p = mv$ and v indefinitely. The notion of work being converted to KE and p is a powerful one which one might suggest should be retained. In such a case, imposing the idea of an upper bound on speed is not only impossible in the Newtonian equations (if KE and p increase), but we argue that there must be a physical notion of how speed may be kept constant, once it reaches a certain limit.

The definition of speed/velocity is:

$$dx/dt \quad ((1))$$

If one imagines an upper bound speed b , then dx and dt remain the same or increase proportionally even as E and p increase. (Here E and p cannot be given by Newtonian formulas.) The notion of a proportional change in dx and dt seems to be consistent with an increase in E and p . In other words, we suggest that for an object moving at the upper bound speed b , E and p may actually regulate dx and dt which appears to be a physical feature which may be measured (as in 2-slit interference).

We argue that E and p may be measured independently in the usual Newtonian way through perhaps heat generation and impact on a target. The upper bound on speed condition suggests that they may be measured in another way linked to space-time related interactions because they now also control dx and dt .

Thus, work is done on a particle with rest mass to increase its E and p until it reaches the upper limit speed of b . At the point it reaches speed b , E and p also control dx and dt linked directly to speed such that one cannot increase dx/dt . If this is true, however, for a speed slightly less than b , one would also expect E and p to be linked with gradations dx and dt , but the ratio dx/dt would no longer be $b - \delta$. In other words, the feature of controlling dx and dt gradations might be a physical condition which holds for all speeds. We argue this because for low speeds, there should be the sense of an upper bound limit on speed. If one has equations (e.g. special relativistic equations). If this were not the case, then one could use any value of v in such equations, hence contradicting the notion of an upper bound $b=c$.

Lorentz Transformation Based on an Upper Bound of Speed

In Newtonian mechanics, one has the Galilean transformation which does not allow for an upper bound on speed. This begs the question: Why consider an upper bound speed limit? We suggest that even if one considers a particle with rest mass, m_0 , at rest at $x=0$, t and describes it as seen by a frame moving with constant $-v$, one must introduce a constant b (speed units)

which is the same for all frames. A speed which is the same in all frames is one which is not changed, i.e. not increased and so seems to represent an upper bound. (The lower bound is 0.)

Thus, for m_0 at $x=0$, t , in the moving frame one must have:

$$x'/t' = v \quad ((2))$$

This suggests: $x' = g(v/b) v/b t$ and $bt' = g(v/b) t$ ((3))

Here one creates a vector with the components having the same units, i.e. (x, bt) . In other words, b emerges, but it is not clear what it represents.

We suggest that one start with the a priori notion of an upper bound on speed. This seems to suggest:

$$x/t = b \quad \text{and} \quad x'/t' = b \quad \text{for} \quad x=0, t=0 \quad \text{transformation to} \quad x'=0, t'=0 \quad ((4))$$

This is unusual because according to the Galilean transformation, the moving frame should create the sense of speed, but this only holds for a particle with rest mass. If there is an upper bound speed b , it cannot be augmented by a moving frame viewing it. The definition of speed is dx/dt or $(x-0)/(t-0)$ and so something other than the moving frame must be controlling the dx and dt values. The question becomes: Can one create a transformation using ((4)) and a frame moving with $-v$?

In ((4)), even though there is an upper bound on speed, (x,t) and (x',t') represent co-ordinate axes which are like rest mass objects. Thus, the co-ordinate x and t values may change in the usual $m_0 \neq 0$ way, but not the ratios in ((4)), i.e. speed. The problem is that one would have:

$$x = bt \quad \text{and} \quad x' = g(v/b)x + g(v/b)vt \quad t' = g(v/b)v x + g(v/b)t \quad \text{where} \quad v \rightarrow b \quad \text{The ratio} \quad x'/t' = b.$$

Here one assumes a matrix of:

$$\begin{vmatrix} g & vg/b \\ vg/b & g \end{vmatrix} \quad ((5))$$

$$Xx - ttbb = gg\{ (x+vt)(x+vt) - bb (vx/b+t)(vx/b+t) \} \quad \text{for} \quad v \rightarrow b \quad ((6))$$

Essentially implies that:

$$(xx - ttbb) = gg (xx - bbtt) (1 - vv/bb) \quad \text{or} \quad g(v/b) = 1/\sqrt{1 - vv/bb} \quad ((7))$$

Thus, by using an upper bound limit on speed and the notion of a rest frame applying to co-ordinate axes one may find ((7)). The idea of an upper bound on speed is directly intertwined with the notion of a rest frame. As a result, ((5)) should apply to both a particle with the upper bound speed b as well as a particle with speed v .

At this point, there is no physical reason for an upper bound limit b to exist. For example, there is no reason that dx may increase more than dt . It doesn't for ((5)) because one imposed $x/t=b$, $x'/t'=b$ for the no rest mass scenario. We suggest, however, that if ((5)) applies to a rest mass case, it also should apply to m_{0b} and $p=0$ in the rest frame (as mimicking $x=0, t$). Then, one finds that:

$$E = p b + m_0 b \quad \text{where } E = m_{0b} / \sqrt{1 - v^2/b^2} \text{ and } p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/b^2} \quad ((8))$$

For $m_0=0$, which applies to the upper limit b case, one has: $E = p b$ ((9))

((9)) is an unusual equation, we argue, in that it links E and p in a dynamic spacetime manner, i.e. mimics:

$$x = b t \quad ((10))$$

In the case of an upper bound speed b , one wants E and p to increase, but b to remain the same. A consistent way for this to happen is through ((9)), i.e. through E and p actually controlling dx and dt intervals required to create speed and not through a Galilean view of a moving frame. Then:

$$dx = \text{constant}/p \text{ and } dt = \text{constant}/E \quad ((11))$$

In other words, ((11)) is dictated by the upper bound constraint. We argue, however, that this result should hold for v values slightly lower than b if it is a physical phenomenon, but one no longer has:

$$((11)) \text{ and } dx/dt = b - \delta \quad ((12))$$

((11)) may be a physical manifestation of the upper bound speed b limit which holds for all v , even with dx/dt (from ((11)) no longer yielding v because this now comes from a rest mass m_0 and speed as being seen as being created by the moving frame $-v$. Even in such a case, as $v \rightarrow b$, the moving frame can no longer increase speed as argued above. In such a limit, $m_0 \rightarrow 0$ compared with the energy due to $v \rightarrow b$.

The physical importance of ((11)) is that it maintains the notion of an upper bound speed for all v with rest mass and for b with no rest mass through p and E defining, physically, gradations in space ((11)). These, we argue, are the basis for free particle quantum mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Newtonian mechanics suggests that $KE = .5mv^2$, $p = mv$ and v may increase indefinitely as one applies work to a particle. This is linked with the notion of a Galilean transformation. We argue that creating a Lorentz transformation for a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0, t$ such that $x'/t'=v$ (as seen by a frame moving with constant $-v$) leads to the presence of

a constant b (velocity units) which is the same in all frames. If this is a physical speed, then it violates the Galilean transformation and the idea that one may apply work and increase its value. We suggest that b is compatible with an upper bound on speed. We then show that one may obtain the same Lorentz transformation assuming $x/t=b$, $x'/t'=b$ for this $m_0=0$ particle (because there is no rest frame). We argue that for b , it is not the moving frame which gives the sense of b , but one must consider dx and dt in dx/dt specifically. We suggest that if E and p increase, but b remains constant, then a possible solution is that E and p regulate dx and dt . If one applies the Lorentz transformation to (pb, E) one finds: $E=pb$ in the $m_0=0$ case. This mimics a dynamical equation and is consistent in suggesting that $\text{constant}/E = dt$ and $\text{constant}/p = dx$. In other words, dynamical variables control dx and dt which are linked to speed for b , the maximum speed. For lower speeds, an m_0 comes into play and dx/dt is no longer v , but we argue that the notion of $dx=\text{constant}/p$ and $dt =\text{constant}/E$ may still exist as the physical conditions for an upper bound on speed. In other words, this physical basis of this constraint is already seen for all v and is physical. We suggest that this gives rise to free particle quantum mechanics.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. $m_0 \cdot c$ Transforming as Time in Special Relativity and the Notion of E, p and Free Particle
Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2025)